

SOCIO-PEDAGOGICAL BASIS OF IMPROVEMENT OF FINE ART EDUCATION IN GENERAL SECONDARY SCHOOLS

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В статье даётся теоретический анализ улучшение социально-педагогических требований в изобразительном искусстве. Здесь говорится о значении и особенностях принципов, используемых в изобразительном искусстве. Также совместно с этим изучены социальные принципы улучшение педагогических особенностей в изобразительном искусстве.

Theoretical analysis of social-pedagogical requirements improvement is given in this article. The importance and particularity of principles which are used in learning Art is analysed as well. Social principles of improvement pedagogical particularities in teaching Art are spoken in this article.

Ushbu maqolada tasviriy san'atdagi ijtimoiy-pedagogik talablarning yangilanishi nazariy tahlil qilingan. Tasviriy san'atda qo'llaniladigan tamoyillarning ma'nosi va xususiyatlari haqida so'z boradi. Shuningdek, bu bilan birgalikda tasviriy san'atdagi pedagogik xususiyatlarni modernizatsiya qilishning ijtimoiy tamoyillari o'rganildi.

It is necessary to pay special attention to the pedagogical principles of education when selecting materials for fine art education. In particular, the principle of scientificity should be in the center of attention. After all, any visual art material acquires a certain degree of scientific and historical value and importance. Also, the principle of regularity and sequence ensures the formation of students' knowledge of visual arts in an integral connection with each other.

The selection and use of fine art materials and national artistic traditions is also based on the principle of scientificity, which is one of the important principles of pedagogy.

The teaching process of fine art material and national artistic traditions is the most important and necessary. Materials should be consciously mastered by students, encourage them to overcome difficulties, activate their mental and physical strength.

This principle takes into account the level of complexity of the studied materials and the age characteristics of the students. It should be considered that the age indicators of psychological development are very variable.

If this feature is not taken into account, the acquisition of knowledge, skills and abilities will be much more complicated. Therefore, this process requires teachers to have professional knowledge, in-depth pedagogical knowledge and methodical experience in raising and teaching children. This, in turn, is also noted separately in State educational standard.

In the education of visual arts, it is important to explain the nature of visual art to students, based on concrete evidence, to form concepts about art, the form of social consciousness, and special activities aimed at artistic reflection of existence.

As a preliminary condition for the work of fine art on art, it should be understood that any kind of art is an understanding of the universe according to the laws of beauty. Beauty is not only an aesthetic content, but also an image filled with a specific ideological and emotional content. We can see such an image in the elements of the black hat pattern. The captivating charm of its unique shapes and colors is perfectly matched by the fact that some patterns have a mythological history. Independent teaching of the peculiarities of Karakalpak patterns and the harmony of colors in the course of the lesson and in extracurricular activities is considered a small scientific work done by the students. It is not surprising that the student's ability to comment on the art samples of his nation, his interest and respect for his history will serve as a bridge for the creation of great scientific works and scientific innovations in the future.

The art that gradually appeared, developed and enriched in different historical periods of the multinational state appears as a special integral part of the artistic culture in each separate country, region, and district of the country. Artistic creations of the past are unique documents of ideological, political, moral, intellectual, artistic and aesthetic activities of the people of the past, and they preserve a great spiritual heritage that instills feelings of pride and love for the Motherland.

Our country is rich with works of art, painting and sculpture in every country, with easel painting and monumental sculpture, with various artistic works on metal and wood, with aesthetically valuable objects.

These diverse art materials, which reflect the intellectual and spiritual strength of our people, form the collections of museums, art galleries, private art gatherings, local fine arts and art museums. Many cities and remote villages still amaze us with the beauty of their rich historical architectural ensembles and nature reserves.

It is important to pay attention to its social function in the interpretation of art in the work of fine art, because it participates in solving the specific tasks of social practice of learning and updating the world, serves the interests of the people, can be a source of joy and happiness.

The scope of issues in aesthetic education and upbringing should be introduced to students with the concepts of ideology, citizenship, ideological artistic content, ideological-thematic unity, social relevance, national identity and the essence of national art, which takes into account the universal content

of works of art.

When mastering the categories of the creative process, special attention should be paid to understanding the close connection between the ideological and artistic content of the work and the artistic language and artistic expression. It is also very important to understand the essence of the creative process in the form of composition sketching, preparation of nature drawings and color sketches, and the moment of finishing the work of art.

In the process of visual art work, students understand the important direction in literature and art, strengthen the connection with the life of the people, and make a correct assessment of social existence.

In visual arts classes, the study of art objects and architectural monuments one after the other should be conducted on the basis of general pedagogical principles, in particular, from simple to complex, from familiar to unfamiliar, etc. The study of any type of folk art in fine arts classes is concerned with determining the ways in which patterns and ornaments developed and spread.

In the study of examples of folk art, it is necessary to determine the social direction of the local masters, the close connection of the works performed individually and as a team with the nature of the country, it also embodies the way of life and customs of the people. Students develop their knowledge of applied arts and crafts by identifying the origins and uses of pattern elements while mastering materials. For example, we can see that the shapes of these folk goods with an elegant taste come to a certain aesthetic shape in the folk goods belonging to each period. Its appearance is filled with pattern element compositions, which is unique for each period. Also, the improvement of these decorative patterns is a proof of the growth of the aesthetic taste of the people. This, in turn, determines the history of the nation.

Introducing students to the practical and decorative features of art prepares them to study wood carving and stone architecture objects. The next step in the mastery of this new material is the study of decorative decoration used in architectural constructions, their exteriors and interiors. Therefore, one of the most important tasks of the study of architectural objects is related to the formation of concepts about the unique features of carving, and the determination of the means of reflecting architectural laws. Concepts about architecture, its tasks, its place in the life of society, opinions about the direction in which the work of carvers should lead are different. Some pay more attention to the practical side of architecture, while others pay more attention to its uniqueness as an art form. Architecture surrounds us all the time, and its images are powerful, so it is important to teach students to understand and feel architecture. Knowledge of the history of architecture, understanding of the richness and diversity of the architecture of our country will help this. Architecture is closely related to the life of its time, it shows the character of the time. Along with studying the architecture of different periods with the students, it is necessary to always explain to them the character of the social system and the formation of the dominant ideology of the architecture. In the formation of architecture, the architectural construction traditions of this place play a major role, the primary importance and focus on social conditions, goals and tasks, with their help, artists should always explain about the use of this or that method and solution.

The most difficult part of fine art work in art is the study of painting, pen painting, easel painting and monumental sculpture. The complexity of fine art work on art is to get acquainted with and study cultural monuments that have artistic value. Most of them are kept in museum collections.

Applied decorative art is characterized by labor and creative processes and has a great educational value. Acquaintance of students with practical decorative items will make them enjoy the creative work of folk masters, and will help them acquire the skills and abilities of artistic processing of various materials.

Fine art work in art is based on the scientific principle of teaching. All work on visual arts is aimed at forming the worldview of young students: to understand the world of art, to understand its relationship with production, politics, science, morality, ideology of all spheres of society, to develop criteria for evaluating the aesthetic qualities of artistic phenomena, to study the causal relations of visual, practical decorative art and artistic culture with the processes of creating other objects building skills, it is considered to determine the originality of visual and material means of creating works of art, applied and decorative art, architectural structures.

In general secondary schools, museums of the motherland, which represent the unique aspects of each region, training sessions on fine arts, drawing according to nature, drawing thematic decorations, establishing the kind of fund needed for art conversations is an important visual art problem. It is necessary to create conditions that ensure active and positive approach to students' inquisitiveness, knowledge, and aesthetic activities in solving any problem.

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